

Is-Ra-El/Vishnu/Shang Di/Shamash

The Cosmic Egg He-She God was a Dwarf Star not our Sun!

“The 1 begat the 2. The 2 begat the 3. The 3 begat the
10,000 myriad things...” ~Dao-de Jing, Verse 42

In the Beginning...

Aside from Logos, what was there?

The earliest idea of "egg-shaped cosmos" comes from some of the **Sanskrit** scriptures. The Sanskrit term for it is **Brahmanda** (ब्रह्माण्ड) which is derived from two words - 'Brahma' (ब्रह्मा) the creator god in Hinduism and 'anda' (अण्ड) meaning 'egg'. Certain **Puranas** such as the **Brahmanda Purana** speak of this in detail.

The **Rig Veda** (RV 10.121) uses a similar name for the source of the universe: **Hiranyagarbha** (हिरण्यगर्भ) which literally means "golden fetus" or "golden womb" and is associated with the universal source **Brahman** where the whole of all existence is believed to be supported.^{[4][5]} The **Upanishads** elaborate that the **Hiranyagarbha** floated around in emptiness for a while, and then broke into two halves which formed **Dyaus** (Heaven) and **Prithvi** (Earth).

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/World_egg

Zoroastrianism mythology

According to Zoroastrian cosmology, the period of (material) creation, also to last 3,000 years, began after the treaty, when [Ohrmazd](#) recited the [Ahunwar](#) (Av. Ahuna Vairiia) prayer, revealing to [Ahriman](#) his ultimate defeat and causing him to fall back into the darkness in a stupor, which lasted for the entire period of the creation. During this time Ohrmazd fashioned his creations in material (*gētīg*) form, by celebrating a “spiritual *yasna*”. He placed each creation under the protection of one of the seven [Amahraspands](#) (Av. Aməša Spənta). First he created the sky (protected by [Šahrewar](#), Av. Xšaθra Vairiia), which enclosed the world like the shell of an egg. The second creation was water (protected by [Hordād](#), Av. Haurvatāt), **which filled the lower half of the “egg.”** The third creation, earth (protected by Spandārmad, Av. [Spənta Ārmaiti](#)), **shaped like a flat disk, floated on the primeval waters.** On it stood the **fourth, fifth, and sixth creations, respectively the single plant or tree** (protected by [Amurdād](#); Av. Aməretāt), the uniquely created bull (protected by [Wahman](#), Av. Vohu Manah), and the first man, [Gayōmard](#) (Av. Gaiiō.marətan, protected by Ohrmazd himself). The seventh creation, fire (protected by [Ardwahišt](#); Av. Aša Vahišta), was said to have permeated all other creations. **During the 3,000 years of the period of material creation these creations were motionless, and the sun stood still in the middle of the sky**

Greek mythology

The **Orphic Egg** in the ancient Greek **Orphic tradition** is the cosmic egg from which hatched the primordial **hermaphroditic** deity **Phanes/Protogonus** (variously equated also with **Zeus**, **Pan**, **Metis**, **Eros**, **Erikepaios** and **Bromius**) who in turn created the other gods.^[7] The egg is often depicted with a serpent wound around it.

Many threads of earlier myths are apparent in the new tradition. **Phanes** was believed to have been hatched from the **World-Egg** of **Chronos** (Time) and **Ananke** (Necessity) or **Nyx** (Night). His older wife **Nyx** called him Protogenus. As she created nighttime, he created daytime. He also created the method of creation by mingling. He was made the ruler of the deities and passed the **sceptre** to Nyx. This new Orphic tradition states that Nyx later gave the sceptre to her son **Uranos** before it passed to **Cronus** and then to Zeus, who retained it.

Egyptian Mythology

The ancient Egyptians accepted multiple creation myths as valid, including those of the Hermopolitan, Heliopolitan, and Memphite theologies. Under the Hermopolitan theology, there is the Ogdoad, which **represents the conditions before the gods were created** (Van Dijk, 1995). An aspect within the Ogdoad is the Cosmic Egg, from which all things are born. Life comes from the Cosmic Egg; **the sun god Ra was born from the primordial egg in a stage known as the first occasion** (Dunand, 2004).

Who were these gods? In order...

Ra - Brahma - Ooranus - El > Kronos > Hera “Saturn”

Osiris - Vishnu - Zeus - Odin - “Jupiter”/Horus/Marduk/Ba’al/YHVH

Hathor - Shiva - Poseidon - “Neptune”

Set/Anubis - Hades - “Uranus”

What does the rock art and glyphs tell us?

- There was one egg shaped orb ~ ratio of 1.23
- It stretched out, and developed a bulge, around 12,000 years ago (Gobekli Tepe), Go to between 1.44 and 1.56 in ration, and began to flatten on the bottom and the left side; the bulge in the northern part grew
- The egg lengthened as far as 1.7-2.1, before splitting into two very large spheres, and there was a corona around both
- This took ~3000 years. The next phase involved the larger egg birthing Neptune or Uranus; most likely Neptune based on ratio evidences
- Somehow Earth ended up with Saturn as the center star, and the TRIAD formed a perfect triangle. It is unclear where Uranus went/hid

For a brief period...

- Neptune/Poseidon/Enki was the star-lord, probably indicating a unique rotation of perspective over time
- Eventually the minor gods, such as Metis, Thoth/Hermes, and others would come into view then move away
- There was no need for a sun “Sol” because the glow post dwarf star was augmented by the solar light, and reflected down, but also Neptune and Saturn glowed strongly
- Jupiter remained aloof, and only later did “Enlil” make its presence known
- If it is not perfectly clear that Marduk couldn't be Hades/Uranus
- Kronos was the Ra, the “Lord of Diadems” until wrestled and castrated

The Great Flood, a great perspective shift

- Atrahasis says Enlil knew it was to come and ordered Enki not to say, but he hinted at it to Zirusthustra
- So we see that Poseidon gave some hint of the changes coming
- Earth LEFT Saturn, passed through the rings, and approached Enki/Jupiter
- Jupiter's moon, the Moon Sin, appeared to move towards Tiamat.
- The Earth's moon, Kingu, was destroyed, and the small satellites were absorbed by Jupiter.
- Jupiter also stole moons from Saturn and maybe the other gas giants
- Thus the Great Deluge was the result of the transition from 7kya-4kya in control of our orbit from Kronos to Zeus

Betrayers and punished Demigods

- Hodr was banished, just as Hades was
- Set was revenged upon by Horus
- Metis was destroyed
- Triton the moon ended up in retrograde, as well as one moon of Jupiter within the retrograde orbit ended up in prograde.
- Uranus ended up on its side
- Mars and something else (Heimdallr/Mercury) were castrated from Saturn and Kronos became Hera
- Quetzalcoatl was “sad” and set himself on fire and Venus erupted from Saturn and finally it died; the green glow went with Venus.
- Numerous demigods punished by Hera for betrayal with Zeus, and “transformed”

The 3 became the 10,000 things

The first triad religion was of the three gas giant gods; with Hades/Uranus in the background

Later this religion was revitalized when Mars, Mercury, and Venus became a new triad.

The Father begat the son, who became Father and begat the son,

The sun/Sol approached and the Sun/Moon dichotomy changed the previous religious orders of the world.

Father-Son was modified into an abstract concept; originally it was a breakdown of the star.

Evidence Chain

1. Measure equatorial :: polar diameters (and compare to satellite measures)
2. Ratio always ≥ 1
3. Ramesses II stele is “gold standard”, 1.23 egg; Jupiter and Saturn 1% of satell.
4. Ratios appear to vary from 1.17 to 2, with modes near 1.21, 1.44, 1.58, and 1.71
5. Eggs show these features: not circles, flat butts, flat bottoms, “chick” hatching, and of course, extension in length
6. Split “owl eye” motifs show strong coronas
7. Also so do Concentric Circle motifs
8. Ratios belonging to 1.04 are taken to be non-Jovian, non-Saturnian gas giant
9. Ratios of 1 cannot be determined, except coronas cannot be rocky bodies

F. J. Gardner, 1881 from a drawing by H. G. Ladd

SMALLER TABLET BETWEEN THE FORE LEGS OF THE SPINNY.

Table 1: Comparisons of X/Y ratios of 3 stele

	<i>Ramesses Stele</i>	<i>Ramesses II</i>	<i>Chia Stele</i>	<i>Average</i>	
X	0.4852	0.799	0.861	0.715	
Y	0.393	0.694	0.692	0.593	
X:Y	1.23	1.15	1.24	1.21	
Stand_Dev	5.11%				

Table 2: Solar, Jovian, and Saturnian Comparisons and Standard Deviations

	<i>Sun (km)</i>	<i>Jupiter</i>	<i>Saturn</i>	<i>Ratio J:S</i>
X	1,391,982.8	142,984	120,536	1.186234818
Y	1,391,972.8	133,709	108,728	1.229756824
X:Y	1.000007184	1.069367058	1.10860128	
C_X		0.259	0.2475	1.046464646
C_Y		0.245	0.224	1.09375
C X:Y		1.057142857	1.104910714	
Stand_dev		0.86%	0.26%	
Avg C & Real		1.063254958	1.106755997	
Stand_dev vs. Stele		10.38%	7.30%	

Evidence Sites (not incl. Rock art)

Going to show you some of the oldest sites:

- Gobekli Tepe
- Durrington Walls / Stonehenge
- Maputo
- Bakoni
- Li Muri, Sardinia
- Tarxien, Malta
- Lexington, KY
- New Zealand / Tasmania
- [Nabta Playa](#)
- [Monkton up Wimborne, Swindon](#)

Monkton Up Wimborne

Nabta Playa

Les vases étrusques

Les vases étrusques sont des récipients en terre cuite, généralement en forme de coupe ou de vase, utilisés par les Étrusques. Ils sont souvent décorés de motifs géométriques et de figures humaines. Les Étrusques ont hérité de ces vases des Grecs et les ont adaptés à leur culture.

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Tasmania

<https://www.aboriginalheritage.tas.gov.au/Documents/AHT%20Fact%20Sheet%20-%20Rock%20Markings.pdf>

Tasmania Aboriginal Rock Art

Aboriginal rock marking (engraving)

Lexington

ANCIENT WORK, FAYETTE CO. KENTUCKY.

No. 3.

C. Rafinesque del.

Malta

Sardinia

Li Muri

complex

Bakoni

Maputo

Durrington Walls

Stonehenge

Gobekli Tepe

Vulture Stone #43

Note dual pillars and

Compare to Sardinia

Enclosure C

Enclosure A

An aerial photograph of an archaeological site showing four circular enclosures, labeled A, B, C, and D. Each enclosure is a circular pit with a raised earthen wall. Enclosure A is at the top right, B is in the middle right, C is in the middle left, and D is at the bottom. The ground is a mix of dirt and stone. Some enclosures have wooden stakes or poles driven into the walls. A vertical pipe or structure is visible in the upper left quadrant.

Enclosure C

Enclosure B

Enclosure D

Enclosure C

<https://tepetelegrams.wordpress.com/category/from-t>

The oldest enclosure

<https://www.andrewcollins.com/page/articles/Gob>

Untold story, only 5% revealed

What else is there?

Why don't they want to do the rest of the excavation?

Implications

1. Jupiter *cannot* be Nibir; its identity is well shown and banded. Also violates Enuma Elish where Neptune is wife and Jupiter husband beckoning it forward
2. We orbited over Jupiter temporarily because we broke away from Saturn
3. Moon is a jovian body, as we approached it created megatsunamis
4. Saturn's ring material created the deluge
5. This is a different event, most likely, than the YDE melt; and than the physical flip
6. The sudden change of the breakdown of the "benben" triangle/triad caused YDE
7. The coronal discharge of the God Flare -> Thunderbolts; one hit earth that was capable of shaking everything
8. Later rocky objects approached with the moon, hence "thundereggs" (part 1)

cont'd

1. The event lasting 3,000 years was first a splitting, then a bubble dropping plasma down to fill up Neptune
2. Uranus **may** have been Nibiru, or may have formed from gaseous siphoning
3. The stamp of Marduk is a Jovian thunderbolt from our close approach (see octagon stamps)
4. The Richat is most likely a Jovian discharge of the 7kya boundary but it could be older
5. The Sahara sand dropped on Earth is probably lunar in origin, not Martian because Martian dust grows plants well.
6. The event was a multi-stage breakdown, maybe RHYTHMIC, but not CYCLIC
7. It was relatively unpredictable. Once over, the Tepeans buried the knowledge and moved on with living, in caves?? Worldwide tree growing 7kya-3.5kya

Timeline

- ❖ 12.5 kya Sun approaches, begins flare event
 - Rise in plasma activity leads to Pyramidic sciences
 - Collapse of Atlantis, and other landmasses, probably crustal deformations under solar collapse
- ❖ 9 kya Ooranus/Ra/Shamash splits, forms Jupiter, then Neptune (Hindu/Sumer holy Trinity)
 - People live underneath the ground, likely from radiation threat
 - Earth slowly transitions out of formed conjunction; Neptune/Rama/Poseidon briefly acts as God
 - Hades (Uranus planet) born? Or approaches with sun? Probably extrasolar, Set perhaps?
- ❖ 7 kya Earth leaves Saturnian system, approaches Jupiter.
 - Climate change / formation of Sahara (mostly moon dust); discharges shared Earth to Moon
 - Thunderbolt “stomp” (of the God’s foot) ; see [Megafauna Extinction Paper](#)
 - Zeus appears to “wrestle” Kronos*; Kronos “castrated” becomes Hera
- ❖ 4.5 kya Sol/Apollo approaches “lion god” motif (ripping intestines out of a god)
 - “Grows like a child” > Father>son>Father>son>Sun
 - Concentric circle = flares? (so misnamed ‘micronova’?)
 - Rise of Solar and Lunar worship
 - Venus Rampage? ([birthed from Saturn](#))
- ❖ 3.5 kya Mars disrupts Venus, ends Jovian Reign, “War of the Gods”; Heracles HEROism
 - Dark Ages from Venus tail; Near end of the World; Medusa/etc.; Jupiter vaporizes whole cities
- ❖ 2.7 kya Mars approaches Earth as whole “new triad” (eagle foot) breaks down and approaches Sol; Gas giants long settled in new role. Marduk role transferred many times

Details to fill in...

Many details in my papers

New paper forthcoming with all the data in it

Need to figure out the EXACT genesis for Hades/Planet Uranus; is it Nibiru?

Need to fine tune the Electric Star process/role of discharge, cavitation, etc.

Need to dive into Vedas (in process) and Apollo myths

Need to identify as many perfect circle concentric motifs and compare all ratios of radii eg. Biggs Site vs. Paracas vs. Stonehenge etc. This will fine tune the Sun's entry and when our sky changed color and when the Earth flipped over in a new Electric Field